

WHAT EVOKES YOUR EXPERIENCES?

Hyangah Kim[^] / Hyeon-Jeong Suk[^] / Hyunjin Lee*
KAIST[^] / Hongik University*
hakim2004@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

For the last several decades, User Experience (UX) has been dealt as the interaction between a single user and a product. Recent studies have investigated the social nature of user experiences and pointed out that design researchers need to understand user experience as social interaction between groups of people around artifacts. To understand how people communicate in their experiences with artifacts, this study investigates what characteristics of the shared experiences evoke the viewers' experiences.

Our findings indicate that normal and familiar experiences help evoking process. Interestingly, creative uses given to the viewers help evoking their own creative use experiences. Furthermore, the product used in the shared experience is the key in the evocation process.

Keywords: Use Experience, Sharing experience, Co-experience.

INTRODUCTION

For the last several decades, User Experience (UX) has been one of the most frequently used phrases in the HCI area (Hessenzahl & Tractinsky, 2006). Recent studies have investigated the social nature of user experiences and pointed out that design researchers need to understand user experience as social interaction between groups of people rather than as interaction between a person and an artifact. Groups of people, differently with a single person, communicate with each other, and this communication obviously influences user experience. As internet technology has merged into many aspects of life, the interaction among groups of people has become easier and more active. To understand how social interaction in groups of users influences user

experiences, design researchers need to investigate how experiences are created and how they evolve in the social interaction of users.

EVOKING EXPERIENCES

Battabee and Koskinen (2005) described the three migrations that happen in social interaction: lifting up, reciprocating and rejecting and ignoring experiences as seen in Figure 1. The first, lifting up experiences, means the migration of subconscious experience into "an experience" (Forlizzi & Battabee, 2004). While reciprocating, rejecting and ignoring experiences are easily captured by observing actions, the first process, lifting up experiences, includes sub processes : evoking experiences, evaluating the meaning of the evoked experience, and internally creating a story to be shared with others (Figure 1). These series of processes happen internally, so it is hard to capture how they are processed just by observing. Therefore, this study only focused the first of them, how people evoke their experiences, which are related to the viewers' internal processes, calling back experiences from a series of events in everyday life.

Figure 1. Breaking 'Lifting up experiences' apart into evoking experiences, evaluating experiences, and making a story.

HYPOTHESES

We assume that there are two factors that influence the evoking of viewer's experiences: creative use experiences and the viewer's prior experiences.

CREATIVE USE

When searching for images of 'Duct tape' in a Google image search, most results show unusual and wacky uses of duct tape. In other words, most use experiences shared through the Internet are not unusual or normal. This indicates that unusualness is a dominant feature of experiences shared to others. Therefore, we must confront the question, whether this unusualness is an influential factor on the evoking of viewers' experiences.

Seeing this feature in terms of design, people are using the designed in their own ways rather than in the designed ways. Moran(2002) explains these creative ways as part of the concept of "everyday adaptive design", in which users are engaged at adapting resources at hand. To describe this adaptation, Brandes and Erlhoff (2006) use another term, "Non Intentional Design", which is to say that the design is not an intentional design but just a use. Wakkary and Maestri (2007) observed people's everyday lives and defined their resourceful actions as parts of everyday design.

This study uses a term, "creative use", to distinguish it from normal use which follows the design intent. To investigate the relationship between creative use and a viewer's evoking experiences, we established a hypothesis as follows.

- Creative use experience may help the viewers to evoke their own experience / creative use experience

VIEWER'S PRIOR EXPERIENCE

Forlize and Ford (2000) discussed factors that influence experience: emotions, values, and prior experiences of users, form language, features, aesthetic quality, accessibility of products, context of use, and social/cultural factors. Among these, prior experiences are related to "creative use". In this work, creative uses are defined according to whether they are intended/designed use or not. This criterion is objective; it does not depend on personal experiences. However, when seeing shared

experiences, people cannot identically judge if they are creative or normal. We assume that this difference comes from people's prior experiences. Therefore, a second hypothesis is established as follows.

- Prior experience with shared experience influences the viewer's evoking experience

PLAN FOR EMPIRICAL STUDY

To compare creative use and normal use experiences in terms of their influence on evoking viewer's experience, we selected five creative use cases first as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Five creative use cases selected as stimuli; (from left) A) Hair dryer used for dring socks; B) Pencil used for guessing the answer in an exam; C) Duct tape used for fixing baby as a instant babysitter(listsoplenty.com, 2006); D) Chopstick used for blocking nose(Ichiki and Umehara, 2005); E) Book used for drawing a line

After selecting creative use cases, we also selected very normal cases that use the products used in creative cases as seen in Figure 3.

We designed the questionnaire in order to measure the viewers' prior experience with products and the context in which the product was used in five given cases.

Figure 3. Five normal use cases selected as stimuli; (from left) A) Hair dryer used for drying hair; B) Pencil used for writing; C) Duct tape used for fixing the box; D) Chopstick used for picking food; E) Ruler used for drawing a line

EMPIRICAL STUDY

PARTICIPANTS

Twenty undergraduate and graduate students—ten female and ten male, 18 - 31 years old—participated in the empirical study. It was decided that none of the participants should be design students, in order to remove the designer’s inspiration process, which could influence the results.

FACE-TO-FACE SURVEY

We conducted face-to-face surveys under a controlled environment in order to prevent extraneous factors from influencing the evocation process.

Evoking experiences do not occur alone but in two processes, evaluating the evoked experience and creating a story successively to follow it. To get rid of the evaluation and story making, a survey moderator, one of the authors, continuously guided participants to write down what was evoked in their brain without any judgment.

PROCEDURE

Participants were asked to write down the experiences evoked by given cases. We limited the meaning of ‘experience’ to what participants did, including both direct and indirect experience, which are not imagination, preferences or needs. The survey consisted of five sessions and a questionnaire. A use case is given in each session. Each session can be stopped by a participant who has

no experience evoked by the given case, as well as by the moderator when the participant has no reaction in 30 seconds. Both creative and normal uses were shown in turn to participants in order to compare the influence of creative uses to normal uses on evoking user experiences, which means within-subject-experiment. To reduce the order effect, we changed the order of showing the images to each participant.

The questionnaire was created to examine participants’ prior experiences by asking how frequently participants experienced the products, functions, and contexts in the given cases and how familiar they were with the given cases on the 7 point Likert scale (Figure 4).

RESULTS

We counted the number of experiences noted by participants and checked to see if creative use and prior experiences affected the number of evoked experiences. Later, we also broke the evoked experiences apart into product, function, and context and examined the relationships between the given cases and the evoked experiences.

CREATIVE USE AND NORMAL USE

We conducted a paired sample t-test to compare creative and normal uses in terms of the number of experiences evoked. Normal use experiences evoked more viewer experiences than creative use experiences (Figure 5).

Frequency							
	never	rarely	occasional ly	sometimes	frequently	usually	every time
How often do you use chopsticks?		1	1		3	2	3
Have you ever used any other tool to hold nose?	1	4	2		2	1	
Have you ever held your nose without hands?	2	3	2	2		1	
Have you ever held your nose with chopsticks?	8	2					
Familiarity							
	absolutely unfamiliar	unfamiliar	slightly unfamiliar	neutral	slightly familiar	familiar	absolutely familiar
How much are you familiar with this use?		5	2	3			

Figure 4. Questionnaire asking about participants’ prior experiences. (Numbers denote the number of answers, N=10)

Figure 5. Normal and Creative use of number of the evoked experiences [$t(19)=2.59, p<0.05$]

Additionally, a paired sample t-test was again conducted to evaluate the impact of creative use experiences on evoking viewers’ creative use experiences. There was not a statistically significant increase in the number of evoked creative use experiences between creative use cases and normal use cases (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Normal and Creative use on number of the evoked creative experiences [$t(19)=-0.68, p=0.506$]

To see the details, in the cases of a hairdryer, a pencil, and a chopstick, creative use cases significantly evoked viewers’ creative use experiences ($p=0.042$). In the case of duct tape, most participants marked 0 or 7 points for the question, ‘how fun is this experience.’ In other words, participants showed extreme reactions to this very unusual experience and most female participants felt scared. In the case of the book used to draw a line, participants answered that this case is as familiar as a normal use case.

PRIOR EXPERIENCE

We conducted correlation analysis to understand the relationship between viewers’ prior experiences with the product and the context used in the case and the number of experiences evoked by the case. While there is no significant correlation between the frequency of experiences and the numbers of the evoked experiences, the degree of familiarity that participants marked through the questionnaire showed us that participants had more evoked experiences for familiar cases than for unfamiliar case.

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN GIVEN AND EVOKED EXPERIENCES

The given cases and the experiences evoked by them have similar or identical products, contexts, or functions. Sixty seven percent of the evoked experiences show identical or similar products as those of the given cases.

DISCUSSION

This study discovered that normal uses rather than creative uses significantly evoke more viewer experiences. Besides, it is also found that creative uses are more effective in evoking viewer’s creative use experiences than normal uses. Therefore, since most of the experiences shared through the Internet are creative uses, experiences on the Internet help people’s other creative uses.

This study examined prior experience in terms of both frequency of experiences and familiarity. The results of the empirical study indicate that familiarity with a given case, rather than frequency of experience, helps the viewers evoke their experiences.

This study reveals the cue to evoking viewers’ experiences: Product. This means that, when people see others’ experiences, the product used in them helps them to recall their own experiences.

CONCLUSION

This study explores what characteristics of shared experiences evoke the viewers’ experiences. Our findings indicate that normal and familiar experiences help the evoking process. Interestingly, creative uses given to the viewers help the evoking

of their own creative use experiences. Furthermore, the product used in the shared experience is the key to the evocation process.

This study only focused on evoking experiences, not on sharing experiences. Our findings, therefore, do not mean that normal and familiar experiences are effective at leading viewers to share their own experiences. We are planning further study to examine the relationship between experiences lifted up and those shared.

REFERENCES

- listsoplenty.com (2006) Duct Tape - 1001 Uses
- Battarbee, K. and Koskinen, I. (2005) Co-experience: user experience as interaction. *CoDesign*, Vol. 1, No.1, 5-18
- Brandes, U. and Erlhoff, M. (2006) Non Intentional Design. Daab.
- Forlizzi, J. and Ford, S. (2000) The building blocks of experience: an early framework for interaction designers. Proceedings of the Conference on Designing Interactive Systems: Processes, Practices, Methods, Techniques, August 17-19, New York City, NY, USA, 419-423
- Forlizzi, J., Battarbee, K. (2004) Understanding experience in interactive systems. Proceedings of the Conference on Designing Interactive Systems: Processes, Practices, Methods, and Techniques, August 1-4, Cambridge, MA, USA, 261-268
- Ichiki, H., Umehara, T. (2005) Extra ordinary - an amusing guide for unleashing your creativity. Rockport Publishers.
- Hessenzahl, M., Tractinsky, N. (2006) User experience - a research agenda. *Behaviour & Information Tehcnology* 25, 2, 91-97.
- Moran, T.P.(2002) Everyday adaptive design. Proceedings of the Conference on Designing Interactive Systems processes, practices, methods, and techniques, New York, NY, USA, 13-14.
- Wakkary, R. and Maestri, L. (2007) The resourcefulness of everyday design. Proceedings of the 6th ACM SIGCHI conference on Creativity & Cognition, New York, NY, USA, 163-172